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Sonochemical synthesis, characterization, and bandgap study of nano-sized cobalt (III) coordination complex salts

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Introduction: In the preceding few years, nanotechnology attracts worldwide attention because it offers a huge range of uses and economical potential (1). Therefore, the synthesis of nanomaterials is an important area of research. The properties of inorganic nano-material depend strongly on their morphologies. The growth-control of materials at the nanometer scale play important role in the various field (2). In the literature, several synthetic techniques for the synthesis of nanoparticles are described, including, hydrothermal synthesis, Microwave, and sonochemical technique (3) Among these methods, the ultrasound technique is of great interest because, sonochemistry itself is an application of sonoluminescence and still it has various applications like In degradation, wastewater treatment and in synthesis (4). This article reports the synthesis, characterization, and band-gap study of nano-sized complex salts, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3](\text{SiF}_6)$ (1) & $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3]\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ (2).

Methods: The ultrasound irradiation method assumed the reaction of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3]\text{Cl}_3$ with the sodium salt of hexafluorosilicate or sodium salt of oxalic acid in a 1:1 molar ratio in probe sonicator 20KHz. Synthesized complex salts 1 and 2 were characterized by FTIR, UV-Vis, and SEM techniques. The band-gap value of nano-sized complex salt 1 and 2 was calculated by using Tauc's method.

Results & Discussions: The UV/Vis spectra give two transitions; for nano-sized complex salt 1 and 2, at 517 and 302 nm, and confirm the formation of nano-sized complex salt. SEM image shows that complex salt 1 is a rod shape, with different lengths (fig.1a). However, complex salt 2 is sheet-like (fig.1b). The bandgap values of nano-sized complex salt 1 and 2 were found to be 2.05 eV and 2.45eV for nano-sized complex salt 1 and 2 respectively.

Figure.1. SEM images of (a) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3](\text{SiF}_6)$ (b) $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3]\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$

Conclusions: Nanostructures of complex salts, $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3](\text{SiF}_6)$ (1) & $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{N}_3]\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ (2) have been synthesized via sonochemical route. From band gap calculation, it was concluded that synthesized complex salt 1 and 2 were semiconductors and may find potential application in the field of electronics.

Keywords: Sonochemical process, bandgap energy, semiconductor, cobalt complexes

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